

**FORESTRY
LAND USE
FACTSHEET**

EU MISSION 'A SOIL DEAL FOR EUROPE'

Healthy soils are essential to life on Earth. They are the foundation of our food systems, they also provide clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to climate resilience. Yet, between 60% and 70% of soils in the EU are considered unhealthy. While it can take hundreds of years to form just one centimetre of soil, it can be lost in a single rainstorm or through industrial damage.

The EC launched the Mission '**A Soil Deal for Europe**' - Horizon Europe programme -**to create 100 living labs and lighthouses** in rural and urban areas to drive the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

THE MISSION SOIL WILL¹:

- > Create knowledge and solutions for soil health,
- > Advance the development of a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- > Increase people's awareness of the vital importance of soils,
- > Support the EU's ambition to lead on global commitments, notably the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and contribute to the European Green Deal targets.*

¹ European Commission

[*more information in the Mission implementation plan.](#)

THE 8 MISSION OBJECTIVES

1
Reduce desertification

2
Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

3
Stop soil sealing & increase re-use of urban soils

4
Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

5
Prevent erosion

6
Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

7
Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

8
Improve soil literacy in society

THE MISSION SOIL LIVING LABS ARE...

“user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists, and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption.” Factsheet - EU Mission Soil Deal for Europe: Living labs and lighthouses

CHALLENGES IN FORESTRY LAND USE

Maintaining the ecosystem services provided by forest soils is essential for sustainable forest management. Forest soil health challenges are driven by natural processes but mainly by forest management practices, that are in turn conditioned by socio-economic conditions...

Increasing soil carbon storage (2), reducing erosion and compaction (5), maintaining fertility, and avoiding desertification (1), are only **four examples of soil health related challenges.**

To tackle these challenges and find solutions, there is a need for interaction and co-creation among stakeholders. Living labs aim to tackle these challenges by involving representatives from all members of society to work together.

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN LIVING LABS

An essential feature of Living Labs is their user-centric approach, involving all key actors and end-users throughout the innovation process. While specific participants vary by context, they can be grouped using the **Quadruple Helix Model**—Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil Society—forming a **Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP)** that enables real co-creation and impact.

This inclusive model supports co-learning and ensures that solutions are not only scientifically sound but also practical, economically viable, socially accepted, and environmentally sustainable.

SOME EXAMPLES OF STAKEHOLDERS OF LIVING LABS FOCUSED ON FORESTRY LAND USE MAY INCLUDE:

- **INDUSTRY:** forest owners and land managers, forest contractors, and forest-based companies, water utilities, forest machinery companies, as well as all relevant sectoral organisations such as forest owner, professional and industrial associations in forest related sectors.
- **GOVERNMENT AND PUBLIC SECTOR:** local, regional, and national authorities responsible of forests, including forest and nature conservation services, water authorities and other regulators, public forest advisory and other governmental organisations.
- **ACADEMIA:** researchers in forest management and forest soils, including those from social sciences. Universities, research and knowledge transfer institutions.
- **CITIZENS, CIVIL SOCIETY & USERS:** urban and local citizens, community and citizens representatives, NGOs (e.g. nature conservation protection organisations).

Healthy forest soils are the foundation for carbon sequestration, water regulation, forest productivity and ecosystem stability, making their preservation critical for climate resilience and sustainable forestry.

Key practices for healthy Forest Soils:

- Leave leaves and wood debris to support nutrient cycling
- Encourage mycorrhizal fungi - crucial for tree nutrition, especially in new forests
- Prevent erosion and compaction by limiting exposure and heavy machinery use.
- Regulate recreational use to minimise soil disturbance from vehicles.
- Plan and maintain forest roads to reduce soil loss and water run-off.
- Regulate recreational use to minimise soil disturbance from vehicles.

WHICH ADDED VALUE CAN CO-CREATION BRING IN THIS FIELD?

Forestry Living Labs have the potential to **accelerate the development towards sustainable forest soil management** by finding and developing solutions to tackle soil health issues. Living labs do this by bringing together innovative forest owners, researchers, companies, and citizens. Soil health challenges vary on national/regional and local scale and need to be adapted within the local constraints. **Living labs will provide a platform for all levels of stakeholders to contribute with knowledge, experience, and solutions.** Solutions can for instance be new climate smart sustainable soil management practices to mitigate and/or adapt to climate change or to conserve soil biodiversity. Adaptations of existing practices need to deal with local constraints.

WHICH ACTIVITIES CAN A FORESTRY MISSION SOIL LIVING LAB PERFORM?

Living labs will through collaboration and co-design foster new solutions by:

- supporting experiments under real-life conditions in field experiments within living labs and lighthouses
- initiating and supporting research in controlled laboratories and field experiments
- sharing knowledge and visions among forest soil stakeholders
- identifying feasible actions to maintain and improve soil health

Living labs will provide a platform for

- development of new solutions for soil health challenges
- demonstrating activities for soil health discussions
- fostering collaboration between landowners, managers, contractors, researchers, and public authorities
- co-design processes to design more socio-economically sustainable solutions and overcome regulatory barriers

A tree has roots in the soil yet reaches to the sky. It tells us that in order to aspire we need to be grounded and that, no matter how high we go, it is from our roots that we draw sustenance."

WANGARI MAATHAI

CRITERIA TO IDENTIFY

LIVING LABS*

Aims

- **Innovation, co-creation**, formal learning
- Contribution to **societal challenges**
- **Improving soil health and related ecosystem services** (= > mission objectives)

Participants

Public-private people partnership:

- **Real soil managers** (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holders, etc.) to be at the centre of the innovation process.
- **Other stakeholders:** Associations and organisations with interest in soil health, local or regional government, scientists from a variety of fields outside of soil (natural sciences, social and behavioural sciences), and the wider public.

Activities

- **Co-creation, co-development & experimentation** of innovations improving soil health and related ecosystems
- **Research on impact of these innovative practices on ecosystems**
- **Networking** and **knowledge exchange**
- **Demonstration** (in particular lighthouses)

Context

- Multiple **disciplines** (-> transdisciplinary, inc. social sciences), **methods, dimensions** (technical, economic, social)
- **Place-based** approach and **real-life context** = real farms/forest/urban sites
- **Robust scientific setup** for **ecosystem assessment**
- **Openness**, communication, dissemination

*adapted from McPhee et al. (2021)

LIGHTHOUSES

As lighthouses are sites achieving exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement, the criteria for selecting them will be based on the **mission objectives**, indicators, and thresholds as defined by the monitoring programme:

- **Demonstration, dissemination, and promotion** to soil managers, the public, and the policy arena, at the landscape scale and beyond, of land-use systems that satisfy criteria for sustainable development, in particular in terms of soil health and related ecosystem services.
- Reaching out to the **policy arena** linking results of the Lighthouses to environmental rules and regulations. This is in line with science-based policy support and governance.

HOW TO PARTICIPATE? TWO LIVING LAB TOPICS

1) Brownfield

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01: Living Labs for soil remediation and green redevelopment of **brownfields**

- **Single-stage** submission
- **Deadline:** 30 September 2025
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - should be located in at least three different Member States and/or Associated Countries

2) Biogeographical regions

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01-two-stage: Living labs to enhance soil health in **Continental, Boreal and Alpine biogeographical regions**

- **Two-stage** submission (First, applicants submit a brief outline. Selected proposals are then invited to submit a full application)
- **Deadline:** 4 September 2025 (first stage) and 18 February 2026 (second stage).
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - **Most of the living labs** (i.e., 3 out of 4, or 4 out of 5) must be located **within the chosen region**

Research and Innovation Actions:

100% funding for any actor
Proposals must apply the multi-actor approach
Financial support to third parties is allowed

WANT TO EXPLORE FURTHER?

Biogeographical Regions factsheet

Both Living Lab topics on the SOILL website

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for updates

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SOILL HUB

A collaborative space
dedicated to soil health.

HELPDESK

A wide network of experts
ready to provide guidance and
answers on many topics.